

Day-Night variation in the catchability of rose shrimp, *Parapenaeus longirostris* in the Strait of Sicily: A preliminary investigation

Giacomo SARDO¹

¹*Institute for Biological Resources and Marine Biotechnology (IRBIM), National Research Council – CNR, Via Luigi Vaccara 61, 91026 Mazara del Vallo, Ita*

Abstract

In deep-water areas, decapods still show complex regulation of their swimming and walking activity rhythms in response to diel and seasonal variations in the length of the photoperiod. In particular, light is the major synchronizer of the circadian rhythm in Penaeid family. In this preliminary study the day-night variation in the catchability of *Parapenaeus longirostris* (Lucas, 1846) was assessed.

Keywords: decapod; diel variation; Mediterranean Sea; *P. longirostris*

1. Introduction

Deep-water rose shrimp, *Parapenaeus longirostris* (Lucas, 1846), is an epi-benthic species inhabiting the sandy-muddy bottoms of the bathyal zone between 70 and 400 m of depth (Fischer et al., 1987) and widely distributed in the Mediterranean Sea (Sobrino et al., 2005). In particular, it is distributed in all seas surrounding Italy, predominantly in the Strait of Sicily and the Ionian Sea (Abellò et al., 2002). In the Strait of Sicily, it represents the most important commercial species of the trawler fleet (Sobrino et al., 2005). Indeed, it represents over 60-70% of the total landings (Knittweis et al., 2013).

Many marine species, including decapod, exhibit vertical migration along the water column, ranging from meters to few kilometres (Cartes et al., 1993). In particular, changes in light intensity between day and night, especially at dusk and dawn, appear to be the main factor controlling vertical migration (Ringelberg and Van Gool, 2003). Previous studies have investigated the different catchability rates for *P. longirostris* during the day and night (Carpentieri et al., 2005; Rodriguez-Climent et al., 2016). According to Rodriguez-Climent (2016), daytime catches of rose shrimp were higher than the night-time catches whereas Carpentieri (2005) reported higher catches of rose shrimp during the night. In the current study, short-term changes on a diel scale were analysed in relation to day-night level.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The Strait of Sicily is a transition area connecting the Western Eastern Mediterranean basins. The area is characterized by an intense hydrographic circulation pattern and a complex topography with a stable upwelling system along the shelf edge of the banks and a hotspot of biodiversity of marine species exploited by national and international fleets (Vitale et al., 2018).

2.2. Sampling design and data analysis

A six-day trawl survey in September 2015 was organized by hiring a commercial bottom trawler registered in the harbour of Mazara del Vallo.

In each day, six hauls of 60 minutes each were carried out during day and night between 130 and 159 m at a towing speed of about 3 knots. The vessel was equipped with a traditional polyamide trawl net with a nominal mesh cod-end size of 40-mm square mesh. Thereafter, catches were transported to the laboratory of CNR-IRBIM in Mazara del Vallo where species caught in each haul were identified, counted and weighted.

The Catch per Unit Effort (CPUE) data, as weight of *P. longirostris* individuals per hour (kg/h), were analysed separately for each haul, in order to assess which time periods had similar catch weight. The Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn test were used to assess the difference between total CPUE and hauls grouped according to time period.

Probability level $P < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant. The analysis was

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: giacomo.sardo@irbim.cnr.it (G. Sardo).

conducted in the R Statistical Environment (RStudio software, version 0.99.903 for Windows, Boston, MA, USA).

3. Results and discussion

The comparison of total CPUE by day and night hauls is shown in Figure 1.

The overall weight of *P. longirostris* catches showed significant differences (Kruskal-Wallis test: $P < 0.005$). In particular, the total weight was 131 and 28 kg for day and night hauls, respectively.

Fig. 1. – Total Catch per Unit Effort (CPUE) expressed as kg/h of *P. longirostris* during the day (red) and night (blue) hauls.

In deep-water areas, decapods still show complex regulation of their swimming and walking activity rhythms in response to the day–night cycle and seasonal variations in the length of the photoperiod (Aguzzi et al. 2009). In particular, light is the major synchronizer of the circadian rhythm in Penaeid (Scelzo, 2003). Thus, a variety of structures may be involved in the perception of light. The most conspicuous and best-studied organs are the compound eyes that reach their highest degree of sophistication also in decapod crustaceans (Meyer-Rochow, 2001). According to Hughes (1968), the most obvious advantage of the circadian rhythm controlling emergence and subsequent activity is to confine the times of activity of shrimp to the hours of darkness when predation by fish is minimal. In particular, during the day shrimps feed mainly on detritus and during their nocturnal migration they predate on zooplankton (Sobrino et al., 2005).

Acknowledgements

The data were collected in the framework of the MINOUW project funded by the European Union, H20202-SFS-09-2014 - Towards a gradual elimination of discards in European fisheries (contract n° 634495).

References

Abellò P., Abella A., A. Adamido, S. Jukic-Peladic, P. Maioran, and M. T. Spedicato. 2002. Geographical patterns in abundance and population structure of *Nephrops norvegicus*

(Linnaeus, 1758) and *Parapenaeus longirostris* (Lucas, 1846) (Crustacea: Decapoda) along the European Mediterranean coasts. *Scientia Marina* 66(Suppl. 2): 125-141.

Aguzzi, J., Bahamon, N., & Marotta, L. (2009). The influence of light availability and predatory behavior of the decapod crustacean *Nephrops norvegicus* on the activity rhythms of continental margin prey decapods. *Marine Ecology*, 30(3), 366-375.

Allredge, A. L., & King, J. M. (1980). Effects of moonlight on the vertical migration patterns of demersal zooplankton. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 44(2), 133-156.

Carpentieri, P., Colloca, F., Ardizzone, G.D., 2005. Day-night variations in the demersal nekton assemblage on the Mediterranean shelf-break. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 63, 577-588.

Cartes, J.E., Sarda` , F., Company, J.B., Lleonart, J., 1993. Day-night migrations by deep-sea decapod crustaceans samplings in the Western Mediterranean sea. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 171, 63e73.

Fischer W., Bauchot M.L., Schneider M. Eds. (1987). Fiches FAO d'identification des espèces pour les besoins de la pêche. (Révision 1). Méditerranée et mer Noire. Zone de pêche 37. Volume I. Végétaux et Invertébrés. Publication préparée par la FAO, résultat d'un accord entre la FAO et la Commission des Communautés Européennes (Projet GCP/INT/422/EEC) financée conjointement par ces deux organisations. Rome, FAO, Vo1.1: 267-268.

Knittweis, L., Arneri, E., Ben Meriem, S., Dimech, M., Fiorentino, F., et al. 2013. Stock status and potential yield of deep water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*, Lucas 1846) in the south-central Mediterranean Sea. GCP/RER/010/ ITA/MSM-TD-28. MedSudMed Technical Documents. No 28, 15 pp.

Meyer-Rochow, V. B. (2001). The crustacean eye: dark/light adaptation, polarization sensitivity, flicker fusion frequency, and photoreceptor damage. *Zoological science*, 18(9), 1175-1197.

Hughes, D.A. (1968). Factors controlling the time of emergence of pink-shrimp *Penaeus duorarum* from the substrate. *The Biological Bulletin*, 134(1): 48-59.

Ringelberg, J., and Van Gool, E. (2003). On the combined analysis of proximate and ultimate aspects in diel vertical migration (DVM) research. *Hydrobiologia* 491, 85–90.

Rodríguez-Climent S, Sonderblohm CP, Fonseca P, Erzini K and Campos A (2016). Diel variation in the deep-water rose shrimp *Parapenaeus longirostris* (Lucas, 1846) catches off the Portuguese south coast. *Front. Mar. Sci. Conference Abstract: XIX Iberian Symposium on Marine Biology Studies*. doi: 10.3389/conf.FMARS.2016.05.00073.

- Scelzo, M. A. (2003). Day and night abundance and density of juveniles pink shrimps *Farfantepenaeus notialis* (Pérez-Farfante) and *Farfantepenaeus brasiliensis* (Latreille) in La Restinga lagoon, Margarita Island, Venezuela (Decapoda, Penaeidae). *Nauplius*, 1, 1-13.
- Sobrinho, I., Silva, C., Sbrana, M., & Kapiris, K. (2005). A review of the biology and fisheries of the deep water rose shrimp, *Parapenaeus longirostris*, in European Atlantic and Mediterranean waters (Decapoda, Dendrobranchiata, Penaeidae). *Crustaceana*, 78(10), 1153-1118.
- Vitale S., Milisenda G., Gristina M., Baiata P., Bonanomi S., Colloca F., Gancitaano V., Scannella D., Fiorentino F., Sala A. 2018. Towards more selective Mediterranean trawl fisheries: are juveniles and trash excluder devices effective tools for reducing undersized catches? *Sci. Mar.* 82S1: 215-223.